

THE ROLE OF THE SCHOOL SUBJECT "TECHNOLOGY" IN THE PRIMARY SCHOOL OF PUBLIC EDUCATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Tulganoy Saidnazarova

Teacher of the Department of OTD and labor training

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8301325>

***Abstract.** This report discusses the role of the school subject "technology" in the elementary school of public education in the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

***Keywords:** technological education, personality creativity, technological outlook.*

The subject "Technology" in elementary school plays a special role, as it has a powerful developmental potential. The most important feature of these lessons is that they are built on a unique psychological and didactic base - subject-based practical activity, which serves as a necessary link in the holistic process of spiritual, moral and intellectual development (including abstract thinking) in primary school age. Due to the psychological characteristics of the development of a younger student, the educational process in the course of technology should be built in such a way that the child's productive objective activity becomes the basis for the formation of his cognitive abilities, including sign-symbolic and logical thinking. Only in this way, based on real accounting the functional capabilities of the child and the laws of his development provide the opportunity to activate cognitive mental processes and intensify learning in general.

The value of the subject goes far beyond providing students with information about the "technical and technological picture of the world." With appropriate content and methodological content, this subject can become a base for the formation of a system of universal educational activities in the primary level of a general education school. In this training course, all elements of learning activities (planning, task orientation, transformation, product evaluation, the ability to recognize and set tasks that arise in the context of a practical situation, offer practical solutions, achieve results, etc.) appear in a visual plan and thus become more understandable to children. Subject-practical creative activity, as the meaning of any activity, gives the child the opportunity not only for a detached perception of spiritual and material culture, but also a sense of belonging, a sense of self-realization, the need to master the world not only through content, but also through its transformation. The process and result of artistic and creative activity becomes not the goal itself, but, on the one hand, a means of cognition of the world, on the other hand, a means for a deeper emotional expression of the inner feelings of both the creative child himself and the ideas of the objects of the material world he studies. At the same time, the artistic and creative activity of the child involves all the stages of cognition of the world that are also inherent in adults: observation, reflection and practical implementation of the idea.

The course "Technology" is an integral part of the Educational system "School 2100". Its main provisions are consistent with the concept of this model and solve a set of tasks related to the formation of experience as the basis of learning and cognition, the implementation of search and analytical activities for the practical solution of educational problems of an applied nature, the formation of the initial experience of practical transformational activity. The course is developing and teaching in nature with the priority of the developing function, integrated in its essence. It is

based on a holistic image of the surrounding world, which is refracted through the result of students' creative activity. Technology as a subject is complex and integrative in nature. In terms of content, it assumes real relationships with almost all subjects in elementary school.

Mathematics - modeling (converting objects from a sensual form into models, recreating objects according to a model in a material form, mental transformation of objects, etc.), performing calculations, calculations, building forms, taking into account the basics of geometry, working with geometric shapes, bodies, named numbers.

The world around - consideration and analysis of natural forms and structures as a universal source of engineering and artistic ideas for the master; nature as a source of raw materials, taking into account environmental problems, human activity as the creator of the material and cultural environment, the study of ethno-cultural traditions

Native language - the development of oral speech based on the use of the most important types of speech activity and the main types of educational texts in the process of analyzing tasks and discussing the results of practical activities (description of the design of the product, materials and methods for their processing; narrative about the course of action and building an activity plan; building logically coherent statements in reasoning, justification, formulation of conclusions).

Literary reading - work with texts to create an image that is realized in a product, theatrical performances.

Fine arts - the use of means of artistic expression in order to harmonize forms and structures, the manufacture of products based on the laws and rules of arts and crafts and design.

The purpose of the course is self-development and development of the personality of each child in the process of mastering the world through his own creative objective activity. 353

Course objectives:

- obtaining initial ideas about the creative and moral significance of labor in the life of a person and society; about the world of professions and the importance of choosing the right profession

- assimilation of the initial ideas about material culture as a product of subject-transforming human activity;

- acquisition of self-service skills; mastering the technological methods of manual processing of materials; learning safety rules;

- the use of acquired knowledge and skills for the creative solution of simple design, art and design (design), technological and organizational problems;

- acquisition of initial skills of joint productive activity, cooperation, mutual assistance, planning and organization;

- acquisition of initial knowledge about the rules for creating a subject and information environment and the ability to apply them to perform educational, cognitive and design art and design tasks.

The methodological basis of the course is an activity approach, i.e. organization of the most creative objective activity of children, starting from the first grade. Reproductive is only the development of new technological methods, design features through special exercises.

Sample lesson plan. Each lesson begins with observation, perception of objects of the material and cultural heritage of peoples, samples of future practical work. Their analysis is carried out, first of all, from the point of view of their design features (the number of parts, their shape, type of connection), then - the means of artistic expression (color combinations, selection of

materials, the ratio of the whole and parts, rhythm, etc.). The next technological step is to determine the methods of processing materials to obtain the planned result. Reflection and reasoning in the course of analysis, as the basis of the activity approach, implies the creation of one's own image of an object, the search through sketches of its appearance, design features, the rationale for the manufacturability of a particular material chosen, the determination of rational ways (necessary technological operations) of its manufacture, the determination of the sequence of practical implementation of the plan, solution of technical and technological problems. Practical manipulative activity involves the development of the basic technological methods necessary for the implementation of the plan, and the qualitative embodiment of the plan into a real material object. Particular attention is paid to the formation of elements of work culture among students.

Various types of practical work performed by students must meet the same requirements - practical significance (personal or public), accessibility, aesthetics, environmental friendliness. The teacher has the right to include his own variants of products, taking into account the regional component and his own aesthetic interests.

An important part of the practical work are exercises to master the basic technological methods and operations that underlie the manual processing of materials available to children of primary school age. Exercises are the key to high-quality performance of holistic work. The techniques mastered through the exercises are included in the practical work on the manufacture of products.

The proposed course "Technology" provides for the following types of work:

- the simplest observations and studies of the properties of materials, methods of their processing; analysis of structures, their properties, principles and methods of their creation;
- modeling, designing from different materials (according to a model, model);
- solving available design and technological problems (defining the search area, searching for missing information, determining the range of possible solutions, choosing the optimal solution), creative artistic tasks (general design, design);
- the simplest design (acceptance of an idea, search and selection of the necessary information, the final image of the object, determination of the design features and manufacturing technology of the product, selection of tools, materials, choice of methods for their processing, implementation of the idea with adjustment of the design and technology, testing the product in action, presentation (protection) of the process and result of work).

The regional component in the course is realized through acquaintance with culture and various types of creativity and work, the content of which reflects the local history orientation. These can be products related to the crafts and crafts of the area, other cultural traditions.

The activity of students initially has mainly an individual character. But the proportion of collective works is gradually increasing, especially creative, generalizing projects. Particular attention is paid to the issue of monitoring educational results, evaluating the activities of students in the classroom. The activity of students in the classroom is two-sided in nature. It includes creative thinking work and a practical part for the implementation of the plan. The quality of each of the components often does not match, and therefore often there cannot be one mark per lesson. For the successful advancement of the child in his development, it is important both to assess the quality of his activities in the lesson, and the assessment that reflects his creative searches and discoveries in the process of contemplation, reflection and self-realization. The mastered subject knowledge and skills are assessed, as well as universal learning activities. The results of practical

work can be evaluated according to the following criteria: the quality of the implementation of individual (learned in the lesson) techniques and operations and work in general. An indicator of the level of formation of universal educational activities is the degree of independence, the nature of the activity (reproductive or productive). Creative searches and discoveries are encouraged in a verbal form of approval.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. Together with the brave and noble people, we will build our great future. M.: NOIU "Uzbekistan", 2017.
2. Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2017 No. 187 "On approval of state educational standards for general secondary and secondary specialized, vocational education". Collection of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2017.
3. Muslimov N.A., Sharipov Sh.S., Koisinov G.O. Methods of teaching labor education, career guidance. Textbook. M.: TDPU, 2014.
4. Tokhirov O. Technological education is a state educational standard and a methodology for introducing the curriculum into educational practice. Methodical recommendation. M.: RTM, 2017.